

CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13220148>

Abstract. This comprehensive thesis is written on the challenges of teaching English to young learners. The article highlights the lack of qualified English as a second language teachers, deficiencies in educational resources, and differences in language grammar. The thesis covers best practices such as CLT, TBLT, CBI and technology-enhanced learning.

Key words: challenge, proficienced teachers, learner-centred, globally approach.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu keng qamrovli tezis yosh o'quvchilarga ingliz tilini o'rgatishdagi qiyinchiliklar mavzusida yozilgan. Maqolada malakali ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'rgatuvchi o'qituvchilarining yetishmasligi, ta'lim resurslaridagi kamchiliklar, til grammatikasidagi farqlar to'g'risida ta'kidlangan. Tezis CLT, TBLT, CBI kabi eng yaxshi amaliy usullarni va texnologik takomillashtirilgan ta'limni yoritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: muammo, malakali o'qituvchilar, o'quvchilarga yo'naltirilgan, global miqyosda yondashuv.

Аннотация. Эта комплексная статья написана о проблемах преподавания английского языка молодым учащимся. В статье подчеркивается нехватка квалифицированных преподавателей английского как второго языка, недостатки образовательных ресурсов и различия в языковой грамматике. В диссертации рассматриваются передовые практики, такие как CLT, TBLT, CBI и обучение с использованием технологий.

Ключевые слова: проблема, опытные учителя, ориентированный на учащегося, глобальный подход.

Introduction. Teaching English to children is undoubtedly a rewarding yet challenging endeavor. In today's rapidly evolving world, the importance of English language instruction for young learners remains paramount. Given that childhood is a critical period for language acquisition, it is essential to explore effective teaching approaches that are recognized globally. This thesis aims to identify the challenges faced by primary English teachers both locally and worldwide.

Research on teaching English to young learners has revealed several pressing challenges. One significant issue is the qualification level of English teachers. In many countries, there is a considerable shortage of trained and proficient primary school English teachers. As a result, educators may lack adequate training in general pedagogy or specifically in teaching English to young learners. This situation is particularly acute in impoverished and rural areas.

Literature review. Another major challenge is the scarcity of educational resources in primary schools. Economic constraints often prevent schools from acquiring essential materials such as textbooks, audio and video resources, and language laboratories. For instance, in Li's (1998) study, South Korean teachers expressed concerns about insufficient funding for the equipment and facilities necessary for learner-centered teaching – a sentiment echoed by Turkish teachers in Inal's (2009) research. While it is undeniable that modern technology supporting English instruction has advanced significantly in recent years, many schools still struggle to integrate these resources effectively.

In many parts of the world, large classes are common challenge (Ho, 2003; Wedgwood, 2007; Shamin, 2012), causing teachers to believe it is difficult or impossible to introduce learner-centred teaching because, they have difficulties to monitor students' language use (Li, 1998) or use pairwork and groupwork (Hoque, 2009). A related issue is the problem of control and discipline (Butler, 2005; Littlewood, 2007; Carless, 2004) argues the noise produced during speaking activities can be problematic when the local preference is for quiet and orderly classroom.

Main part. Moreover, another significant challenge in teaching English as a second language (ESL) is the grammatical differences between languages. For instance, while Uzbek is a Turkic language spoken in Central Asia, English belongs to the Germanic branch of the Indo-European language family, which features a more complex grammatical structure.

To address these challenges in ESL instruction, several effective methods have been developed and widely implemented around the world. These approaches can support ESL teachers in enhancing their teaching practices:

1. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): This approach is currently one of the most popular models for English language instruction globally. It emphasizes interaction and communication among learners, fostering a more engaging learning environment.

2. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT): This method utilizes real-life tasks as the foundation for language instruction, helping learners develop the necessary language skills to successfully complete these tasks.

3. Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL): This approach involves simultaneous study of a subject (such as biology, science, or history) and the English language, effectively integrating both disciplines.

4. Cooperative Language Learning (CLL): This method maximizes the use of cooperative activities involving pairs and small groups of learners in the classroom. It encourages children to interact, collaborate, and accomplish tasks together.

5. Total Physical Response (TPR): In this teaching method, the instructor presents language concepts through commands, and students respond by physically acting out the instructions. For example, students might be asked to sit down, stand up, point to objects, or walk to specific locations in the classroom.

Conclusion. Teaching English to young learners presents various challenges, including a lack of qualified instructors, grammatical differences, and insufficient educational resources. To overcome these obstacles, it is essential to provide children with increased exposure to English, enhance the quality of English language teaching, and equip schools with the necessary resources for effective language learning. By implementing these strategies, educators can better achieve their goals in teaching English effectively.

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